

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon EUROPE Programme under grant agreement No. 101075515

DE-RISK Project

D6.2: Project identity, guidelines, logo, branding, social media and website

Project Coordinator: Melike Güllüoğlu (WG)

Work Package Leader: Melike Güllüoğlu (WG)

Deliverable Leader: Melike Güllüoğlu (WG)

Document Information	
Project ID Number	HORIZON EUROPE - 101075515
Full Title	DE-RISK the adoption of Local Flexibility Markets to unlock the safe and reliable mass deployment of Renewable Energy Systems
Acronym	DE-RISK
Project URL	www.deriskproject.eu
EU Project Officer	Charles-Andre LEMARIE
Acknowledgement	The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework programme under Grant Agreement No. 101075515.
Disclaimer	Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Deliverable	Number	D6.2	Title	Project identity, guidelines, logo, branding, social media and website
Work Package	Number	WP6	Title	Wide and High Impact Communication, Dissemination and Market Engagement

Author(s)	Kadir Ülger (WG)
Contributor(s)	Melike Güllüoğlu Lia Michalaki (WG) Irmak Göle (WG)
Reviewer(s)	Juan M. Espeche (R2M)

Date of Delivery	Contractual	31.12.2022	Actual	31.12.2022
Status	E01		Final version submitted to European Commission (EC)	
Nature	R — Document, report			
Dissemination level	PU — Public			

Table of Content

A. INTRODUCTION.....	5
B. ABOUT THE PROJECT	5
C. PROJECT IDENTITY.....	5
1. Project Name	6
2. Project Logo	6
3. Colors and Fonts	7
4. Colours for Visibility Materials.....	7
5. Letterhead and PPT.....	8
D. SOCIAL MEDIA ACCOUNTS	9
1. Social Media Accounts of DE-RISK	9
2. Types of Social Media Post	9
3. Design of Social Media Accounts	10
4. Language in Social Media.....	12
5. Establishment of FlowPage	12
6. HashTag.....	12
7. Reporting of Social Media Accounts	12
E. WEBSITE	12
F. OUTPUTS OF THE PROJECT	13
1. E-Newsletter	14
2. Editorial Contents and Infographics	14
3. Brochures.....	15
4. Promotional Video	16
G. RESOURCES.....	16
H. GENERAL COMMUNICATION PRINCIPLES	16

List of Figures

Figure 1: The logo with the short name of the Project.....	6
Figure 2: The logo usage in different surfaces.....	7
Figure 3: Color codes of logo	7
Figure 4: Fonts of logo	7
Figure 5: Logo colour combinations	8
Figure 6: Letterhead and PPT.....	8
Figure 7: Social media profile pages	11
Figure 8: Social media posts designs	11
Figure 9: Sample website design	13
Figure 10: Sample design of e-newsletter	14
Figure 11: Sample design of brochure	15

List of Tables

Table 1: Social media accounts of DE-RISK.....	9
Table 2: Special days related to environment and energy	10

A. INTRODUCTION

This project identity document was prepared with the aim of defining the project visibility and communication approach the “DE-RISK the adoption of Local Flexibility Markets to unlock the safe and reliable mass deployment of Renewable Energy Systems” project. The approach of this document will be used as a guide by the project team throughout 36 months.

In this document, the "DE-RISK the adoption of Local Flexibility Markets to unlock the safe and reliable mass deployment of Renewable Energy Systems" project will hereby be referred as "project".

B. ABOUT THE PROJECT

The overall objective of the project is supporting the market update of renewable energy systems by fostering the adoption of local flexibility markets (LFMs) and unlocking up to 100GW of flexibility in 2030 which will allow a safe and reliable integration of RES in the grid. DE-RISK will achieve this ambitious objective by minimizing the investments and implementation risk through an innovative customer behavior change journey that will increase end users' trust and willingness to participate in the flexibility markets. DE-RISK integrates building, citizen and grids digital twins in its flexibility platform capable of reducing the gap between simulation and real implementation thus mitigating potential technical risks during deployment and operational phase. To maximize DE-RISK impact, innovative multi-sided business models will be developed ensuring multi-benefits, fairness and sustainability for all actors while disruptive financial schemes will be validated for democratizing the access to sustainable investments. Finally, a set of experts will develop regulatory recommendations to support a fair, clear and transparent adoption of LFMs.

C. PROJECT IDENTITY

The project identity will represent the mission and vision of the project in all kinds of outputs, publications and platforms. The project logo, the colours to be used in the project logo and the visual identity, the letterheads and related draft documents, the diagrams to be used in the printed materials and the designs to be used in all visibility materials will be in unity with the project identity. The use of a standardized visual identity in all project outputs is of critical importance for the public awareness. All designs prepared will be produced upon ensuring the agreement with all project partners.

1. Project Name

One of the most important elements of the project identity is the project name, which will be used for 36 months.

A short name should

- Help being memorable and having a connotation that is informative of the project content,
- Contain a meaning that appeals to the purpose and target audience of the project,
- Be a slogan that can be used directly throughout the project, rather than an abbreviation.

The short name of the project was decided as “DE-RISK”. “DE-RISK” will take place in all visibility materials and product of project.

2. Project Logo

The logo developed and customized for the DE-RISK Project contains color of green and blue. These two colours are the colours that represent nature and clean energy. The transition between colours in the logo creates a soft perception. This representation is an important part of the project identity.

Figure 1: The logo with the short name of the Project

Figure 2: The logo usage in different surfaces

3. Colors and Fonts

Figure 3: Color codes of logo

<p>CMYK: C:31/M:0/Y:100/K:0 RGB: R:188/G:214/B:49 HEX: #BCD631</p>	<p>CMYK: C:66/M:0/Y:100/K:0 RGB: R:117/G:184/B:87 HEX: #758857</p>	<p>CMYK: C:84/M:24/Y:51/K:4 RGB: R:63/G:139/B:133 HEX: #3F8B85</p>
<p>CMYK: C:73/M:19/Y:0/K:0 RGB: R:77/G:162/B:216 HEX: #4DA2D8</p>	<p>CMYK: C:89/M:53/Y:1/K:0 RGB: R:47/G:113/B:178 HEX: #2F71B2</p>	<p>CMYK: C:100/M:93/Y:6/K:0 RGB: R:44/G:60/B:138 HEX: #2C3C8A</p>

Figure 4: Fonts of logo

DE-RISK
 Poppins SemiBold

A B C Ç D E F G Ğ H I J K L M N O Ö
 P R S Ş T U Ü V Y Z
 a b c ç d e f g ğ h i j k l m n o ö p r s
 ş t u ü v y z
 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0

4. Colours for Visibility Materials

All visibility materials to be produced within the scope of the project must be in harmony with the project identity and the aims of the project. The colour used and the design approach should have a holistic structure. For this purpose, it is planned to use the following colours in

the materials produced throughout the project. Different colours that are compatible with these colours can also be used in the materials produced.

Figure 5: Logo colour combinations

Logo Color Combinations

5. Letterhead and PPT

Figure 6: Letterhead and PPT

D. SOCIAL MEDIA ACCOUNTS

Nowadays, social media is one of the most effective means of communication. Thus, it is necessary to set up social media accounts and actively use these accounts to inform the public on aim of the project, to create awareness and to disseminate the activities and outputs of the project. Within the scope of the project, Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and LinkedIn accounts is created on November 2022. A holistic visual design in line with the project identity will be devised for these accounts. These channels will be active during the project. These channels will be used to inform and engage different groups of key stakeholders such as professionals from private enterprises, policymakers, academia, local citizen-led organisations, and citizens at large. All content will be produced considering the needs of the target audience. The language used will be understandable and memorable for the target audience.

1. Social Media Accounts of DE-RISK

Table 1: Social media accounts of DE-RISK

Social Media Accounts of DE-RISK	
Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/deriskproject/
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100088357441737
Twitter	https://twitter.com/DERISKProject
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/87434980/

2. Types of Social Media Post

There will be different type of social media posts.

1. Promotion of project: Especially the first posts will focus on promotion of project. In these posts, information about the aims, activities, target group, duration and implementers of the project will be included. The social media accounts of the project will be promoted at regular intervals and an increase in followers will be achieved.

2. Updates and relevant information about the project: Posts about the current situation in the project, the activities carried out and the planned activities will be prepared.

3. Articles posted on the website

4. Project outputs: Newsletters, infographics, videos, brochures and etc.

5. Special Days: Days related with the scope of the project like World Environment Day will be celebrated with special campaigns.

Table 2: Special days related to environment and energy

DAY	DATE	DAY	DATE
International Day of Forests	21 March	Earth Day	22 April
World Water Day	22 March	World Environment Day	5 June
World Resources Day	23 March	World Ocean Day	8 June
Earth Day	Last Saturday of March	World Energy Saving Day	21 October
World Atmosphere Day	10 April	National Energy Conservation Day	14 November

6. Informative contents: Posts that will raise public awareness about renewable energy systems, energy saving and the effects of energy saving, which are the working area of the project, will be prepared.

3. Design of Social Media Accounts

Simple lines in a minimalist design preferred in social media accounts. The program logo will be used as the logo of each account. There will be a link to the project website in the about us section on all 4 platforms.

Figure 7: Social media profile pages

Figure 8: Social media posts designs

4. Language in Social Media

An integrated, non-political and positive language will be used in all social media accounts. Sharp expressions, contradictory and separatist words will not be used. Attention will be paid to the protection of beneficiary and their activities.

5. Establishment of FlowPage

A FlowPage account will be opened and the relevant link will be pinned to the Instagram profile in order to enable followers to access the links provided on the Instagram post more easily and to increase the number of organic visitors to the website.

6. HashTag

HashTags will be used to increase visibility and engagement. Some hashtags related to DERISK; #sustainability, #energy, #renewableenergysystems, #localflexibilitymarket

7. Reporting of Social Media Accounts

The engagement rates, number of the followers, the interest rates of the contents will be evaluated with periodic social media reports. Reports will be submitted to the beneficiaries in every 3 month.

E. WEBSITE

Nowadays, the internet has become the primary resource for individuals seeking knowledge. Through a website prepared in parallel with the project visual identity; the project, the vision and mission of the project as well as the project outcomes can be disseminated to large audiences. The website will be prepared by following the latest web design practices and design trends and attention will be paid to ensure it is multilingual and accessible for the disabled.

A website with a user-friendly navigation structure will be developed for dissemination the results of the project with the external audience and the stakeholders and creating an awareness on public.

The site URL is “deriskproject.eu”. The website will be easily accessible and sustainable. All kinds of outputs (e-bulletin, infographic, article, video and etc.) produced within the scope of the project will be regularly shared on the website.

Figure 9: Sample website design

F. OUTPUTS OF THE PROJECT

Within the scope of the project, it is planned to prepare different types of outputs. A holistic and harmonious design approach will be adopted in all outputs.

1. E-Newsletter

A total of 6 e-newsletter are expected to be prepared within the scope of the project. These e-bulletins will include information on the latest developments in the project, articles prepared by stakeholders, awareness-raising informative content and project social media accounts.

Figure 10: Sample design of e-newsletter

2. Editorial Contents and Infographics

Each partner will produce a minimum of 1 article, editorial or blogpost during the lifetime of the project based on the work they are doing in the project to summarize key findings and results.

Articles for awareness raising: “on the importance of knowing the energy efficiency of your house and community” and the “how to be part of Local Flexibility Markets and

take advantage of all its benefits” and specialized articles for professional media “Local Flexibility Markets: How to deploy and interact with the energy market” will be written. Articles and relevant material will be uploaded on the website and disseminated via social media channels. These articles will be published in the letterhead design prepared within the scope of the project identity. *(Please, look at Figure 6)*

3. Brochures

As stated in the ToR, brochures with different contents and different standards will be prepared within the scope of the project. The needs of the target groups will be prioritised during the preparation of the contents and design of these brochures. Clear and goal-oriented messages will be included in the brochures.

The same approach will be adopted in the poster and handout materials to be prepared within the scope of the project. A simple and plain language will be used in the materials. In the written materials, the project name will be incorporated effectively in the slogan.

Figure 11: Sample design of brochure

4. Promotional Video

The DE-RISK promotional video will consist of an approximately 2 minutes presentation enriched with infographics and animations, describing the project objectives, the DE-RISK concept and service, and its expected impact. It will be encapsulated on the DE-RISK project website and published on popular video platforms.

G. RESOURCES

The development and implementation of the public website, the establishment of social media accounts and other communication activities are part of the activities in 6.2 and 6.4 task of the project. DE-RISK communication team will support the development, operation and maintenance, as well as monitoring of the website and accounts in social media.

It is also expected that the project partners will be strongly involved in keeping the website up to date. In particular, the project partners will contribute with material and information to be uploaded in the public website and have committed to disseminate the information further (i.e., re-tweet, share, etc.) within their networks.

H. GENERAL COMMUNICATION PRINCIPLES

In all communication activities of the project, the interests and the objectives of the project will be taken into consideration. It is aimed that communication activities will leave a sustainable impact during and after the project. A non-discriminatory, equal and fair language will be used, and sustainability will be prioritized in all concrete and abstract communication materials produced. In particular, the content that references these documents will be shared on the website and social media accounts, which are the first-hand communication tools of the project.

The Communication Strategy Plan produced in the scope of the project will be one of the main guideline and supporting document for Communication and Visibility Strategy.

The project has received funding from the
European Union's Horizon EUROPE Programme
under grant agreement No. 101075515

DE-RISK